

Time domain model for a two-body heave converter: model and applications

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Abstract

This study presents a methodology to obtain the power performance of a two body heave converter. Firstly, the methodology relies on a time domain model which represents the motion of the two bodies throughout the time. This time model was built substituting the entire equation system with a state space system, thereby avoiding the convolution integral of the radiation force. This technique is demonstrated to be a reliable and very efficient method in terms of speed. Then, based on this model the instantaneous power of the device can be obtained. The performance of the device is shown through the power production matrix and the 60 year series power production statistics. This long series is obtained by means of using the MaxDiss selection technique in order to compute only the power of the most representative sea states and the Radial Basis Function interpolation technique (RBF) interpolates in order to obtain the complete power series.

Keywords: State-space, Time Domain, WEC, Heave converter

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1. Introduction

Wave Energy Converters (WECs) generally extract energy from the relative motion between two bodies. In some cases, one mobile part reacts against a fixed or quasi-fixed one as for example the Power Buoy (Ocean Power Technologies) or the Oyster (Aquamarine Power) and in other cases the two parts are reacting among themselves as is the case of Pelamis (Pelamis Wave Power) or the WaveBob.

Wave generation by means of floating bodies can be analyzed numerically using frequency, (see Henriques et al. (2012) or Gomes et al. (2012)) or time-domain models, (see Alves (2012)) being the frequency domain the most widely used due to its simplicity and low computer requirements. Frequency-domain analysis provides the fundamentals of the body motion under regular or irregular waves, but its intrinsic linear approach cannot simulate the floater's behaviour under steep waves, large displacements or rotations and non linear forces associated to the Power Take Off (PTO), turbulent drag or the anchoring system.

To assess the non linear behavior of Wave Energy Converters (WEC) under irregular waves, 3D CFD models can be used with a high computational cost. Another (less accurate and costly) approach is to use numerical models based on the time-domain equations of motion of the floating body, Cummins (1962). In these equations, the wave forces (incident, diffracted and radiated) are solved by an external frequency-domain numerical model, while the rest of the forces can be expressed with all their non-linear characteristics. The

equations solve the time movements of the body, so its true position is taken into account.

The presence of the convolution integral in Cummins equation complicates its solution in the time domain Kashiwagi et al. (2005). To avoid this problem, one of the methods proposed in the literature proposes approximating the convolution integral by a state-space system Yu and Falnes (1995). Taghipour et al. (2008) shows that solving the convolution integral is approximately 8 times slower than using state-space realizations. The problem has moved from solving the convolution integral to finding the elements of the state-space system which approximate that convolution integral. This state-space receives as input the velocity of the body and produces an approximation to the convolution integral as output. Several approaches have been used in the literature, for example Yu and Falnes (1995); Duclos et al. (2001); Kristiansen et al. (2005); McCabe et al. (2005). A description of the different methods can be found in Taghipour et al. (2008). These techniques share a starting point, as all of them require the use of information taken from a 3D Boundary Element Method (BEM) such as WAMIT/WADAM.

The state-space that approximates the convolution integral can be extended to a new state-space that completely replaces Cummins equation Yu and Falnes (1995); Alves (2012). The new state-space receives as input the excitation force and produces as output the movement of the body. A novel alternative, Armesto et al. (2012), does not require BEM codes as it directly identifies the state-space which solves Cummins equation from other sources of information such as laboratory tests or CFD simulations.

The present work uses a model based on Taghipour et al. (2008); Perez and Fossen (2011) to identify the state-space which approximates the convolution integral. This model uses a BEM to compute the added mass and damping coefficients for a given set of frequencies, and then the transfer functions associated to these frequencies is computed. The coefficients of the state-space system are calculated using an identification method in the frequency domain, Perez and Fossen (2009), which meets the requirements given in Perez and Fossen (2011). Finally the state-space is extended to solve Cummins equation Yu and Falnes (1995); Alves (2012). This model is then used to analyze the behavior of the two-body WEC floating in heave presented by Babarit et al. (2012).

First, the numerical model is presented, second the model is validated using the frequency-domain numerical model WADAM, third the time-domain numerical model is applied to check the WEC's performance in a given wave climate and finally, the WEC's PTO damping constant is optimized in order to maximize the extracted energy. In this optimization process, the sea state selection technique MaxDiss and the multi-linear interpolation technique Radial Basic Functions (RBF), see Camus et al. (2011) have been applied.

2. Numerical model description

The WEC geometry to be analyzed in this paper, see the sketch of Figure 1, is a generic two body point absorber consisting of two objects: a buoy (1), that floats on the top of surface and a float (2) that floats mostly under

the surface. Both objects are only allowed to move in heave and the union between the bodies is made via a linear PTO connection.

The time domain model is based on the second Newton law given by equation (1)

Figure 1: Simplified model

$$\sum F = m\ddot{z} \quad (1)$$

where in (1) F represents the external forces, m is the body mass, $z(t)$ is the vertical displacement of the body (z origin at the Still Body Level, SBL) and the dots symbolize the order of partial time derivation. In the case of a generic floating WEC under wave excitation, the external forces in equation (1) were formulated by Cummins (1962), see equation (2).

$$m\ddot{z} = F_{excitation} + F_{PTO} + F_b + F_{rad} + F_{vis} \quad (2)$$

The external forces represented in equation (2) are 1) the wave excitation term, $F_{excitation}$, that results from the integration of the pressure over the wet surface of the body when is held still on the water, 2) the force exerted by the PTO, F_{PTO} , 3) the hydrostatic buoyancy force, F_b , due to the submergence variation caused by the WEC oscillations, 4) the radiation force, F_{rad} , due to the waves radiated by the WEC motion and 5) the viscous friction force, F_{vis} , caused by the turbulent drag generated by the WEC motion in the fluid. The excitation force, $F_{excitation}$ is obtained as explained below using the frequency-domain BEM WADAM. The buoyancy force, F_b , is represented in equation (3) using the hydrostatic restoring coefficient G multiplied by the position of the device.

$$F_b = -Gz(t) \quad (3)$$

The radiation force, F_{rad} , is expressed following Yu and Falnes (1998) in the expression (4)

$$F_{rad} = A_\infty \ddot{z} - \int_0^t K(t - \tau) \dot{z}(\tau) d\tau \quad (4)$$

where A_∞ is the constant added mass when the frequency tends to infinity. The second term is the convolution integral where $K(t)$ represents the fluid memory effects.

The viscous friction force, F_{vis} , is represented following Hals et al. (2007) by equation (5) as a drag force that depends on the vertical velocity difference between the body and the fluid.

$$F_{vis} = B \frac{\pi}{8} C_d D_p^2 (\dot{z} - v_z)(\dot{z} - v_z) \quad (5)$$

where in (5) C_d is the drag coefficient, D_p is the diameter of the body and v_z is the undisturbed flow velocity. Values for the drag coefficient are chosen based on an experimental work by T.Sauder and T.Moan (2007) where the viscous forces were measured for different amplitudes and frequencies. In this work $C_d = 4$ was used.

The PTO force, F_{PTO} , is assumed to be proportional to the relative vertical motion between the two bodies considered as is expressed in equation (6).

$$F_{PTO} = C_{PTO} z_{rel} \quad (6)$$

Inserting equations (3) to (6) in the Cummins equation (2) equations (7) and (8) are obtained for the two bodies considered in this model referred here by the sub-index 1 and 2, respectively

$$\begin{aligned} (m_1 + A_{\infty_1}) \ddot{z}_1(t) - A_{\infty_{12}} \ddot{z}_2(t) &= F_{excitation_1}(t) - Gz_1 \\ &- C_{PTO} [\dot{z}_1(t) - \dot{z}_2(t)] - \int_0^t K_1(t - \tau) \dot{z}_1(\tau) d\tau \\ &- \int_0^t K_{12}(t - \tau) \dot{z}_2(\tau) d\tau - F_{vis_1}(t) \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (m_2 + A_{\infty_2}) \ddot{z}_2(t) - A_{\infty_{21}} \ddot{z}_1(t) &= F_{excitation_2}(t) - Gz_2 \\ &+ C_{PTO} [\dot{z}_2(t) - \dot{z}_1(t)] - \int_0^t K_2(t - \tau) \dot{z}_2(\tau) d\tau \\ &- \int_0^t K_{21}(t - \tau) \dot{z}_1(\tau) d\tau - F_{vis_2}(t) \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

As explained in the introduction, the most challenging task in the resolution of equations (7) and (8) is the computation the convolution integrals inside the radiation force equation (4). An efficient resolution technique is to replace convolution integral with a state-space system, see Henriques et al. (2012) or Alves (2012). A general state-space has the form:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}(t) + \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}(t)\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

where $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ are called input and output respectively of the state space and $\mathbf{X}(t)$ is the state-space vector. Each convolution integral in equations (7) and (8) is approximated by a state-space:

$$I_{ij}(t) = \int_0^t K_{ij}(t - \tau)\dot{z}_j(t) \approx \begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{X}}_{ij}(t) = A_{ij}\mathbf{X}_{ij}(t) + \mathbf{B}_{ij}\dot{z}_j(t) \\ I_{ij}(t) \approx y(t) = \mathbf{C}_{ij}\mathbf{X}_{ij}(t) \end{cases}, \tag{10}$$

$i = 1, 2, j = 1, 2$ where $\mathbf{X}_{ij}(t)$ is the state-space vector and $\dot{z}_j(t)$ is the input of the system.

The problem now is to calculate matrix A_{ij} and vectors \mathbf{B}_{ij} and \mathbf{C}_{ij} that approximated the convolution integral. The methodology is explained for $i = j = 1$. The first step therefore is to choose a set of frequencies $\{\omega_i\}_{i=1}^n$, and compute their damping coefficients, $\{B(\omega_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, added mass coefficients, $\{A(\omega_n)\}_{n=1}^N$, and added mass at infinity, A_∞ with a BEM code. Ogilvie (1964) provides the relations between the transfer function in time domain $K(t)$, and the added mass, $A(\omega)$, and damping coefficients, $B(\omega)$ in frequency domain. Using Fourier transform, it is possible to write the corresponding transfer

function in frequency domain as a function of the added mass and damping coefficients, Taghipour et al. (2008):

$$K_{wadam}(i\omega_n) = B(\omega_n) + i\omega[A(\omega_n)) + A_\infty], \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (11)$$

where i is the imaginary unit. The least square technique is then applied to find a rational function \hat{K} that approximates K_{wadam} for the given set of frequencies $\{\omega_i\}_{i=1}^n$ following the restrictions given by Perez and Fossen (2011). The approximation is restricted to imaginary values, so writing $s = i\omega$, the rational function is defined as (Perez and Fossen (2011)):

$$\hat{K}(s, \theta) = \frac{P(s, \theta)}{Q(s, \theta)} = \frac{p_{n-1}s^{n-2} + p_{n-2}s^{n-2} + \dots + p_1s}{s^n + q_{n-1}s^{n-1} + \dots + q_0}. \quad (12)$$

When the coefficients $\theta = \{p_{n-1}, p_{n-2}, \dots, p_1, q_{n-1}, q_{n-2}, \dots, q_0\}$ are found using the least square method, the matrix and vectors of the state-space which approximates the convolution integral can be written as:

$$A_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -q_0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -q_1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -q_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & -q_{n-1} \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{B}_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ p_1 \\ p_2 \\ \vdots \\ p_{n-1} \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Now, all components of the state-space given in equation (10) are known, and the convolution integral can be replaced by the output, $y_{11}(t)$, of the state-space. However, the heave velocity of the body, $\dot{z}_1(t)$, which is the input

of this state-space system is obtained solving the general motion equation (equations (7) and (8)) of the 2 body WEC every time step. For this purpose, another state-space system is defined (15): the general state-space system, Alves (2012). This state-space describes the general equations of motion (equations (7) and (8)) of the 2 body WEC, taking into account all the forces included, and all the convolution integrals, $I_{ij}(t)$. In order to extend the obtained state-space to a general one, the general state vector collects the state vectors of all convolution integrals and includes the vector of the position, z , and its derivative, \dot{z} :

$$\mathbf{X}(t) = [[\mathbf{X}_{11}] [\mathbf{X}_{12}] [\mathbf{X}_{21}] [\mathbf{X}_{22}] [z] [\dot{z}]]. \quad (14)$$

Finally the general equations of motion (equations (7) and (8)) can be rewritten in an unique state-space as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}(t) + \mathbf{B}F_{excitation}(t) \\ y(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}(t) \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Where the input of the state-space is the excitation force, $F_{excitation}(t)$, the output is the movement of the 2 body WEC, $z(t)$, and matrix A and vectors B and C are given by:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} [A_{11}] & [0] & [0] & [0] & [0] & [B_{r_1}] \\ [0] & [A_{12}] & [[0] & [0] & [0] & [B_{r_{12}}] \\ [0] & [0] & [A_{21}] & [0] & [0] & [B_{r_{21}}] \\ [0] & [0] & [0] & [A_{22}] & [0] & [B_{r_2}] \\ [0] & [0] & [0] & [0] & [0] & [1] \\ \left[\frac{C_{r_1}}{M}\right] & \left[\frac{C_{r_{12}}}{M}\right] & \left[\frac{C_{r_{21}}}{M}\right] & \left[\frac{C_{r_2}}{M}\right] & \left[\frac{G}{M}\right] & [C_{PTO}] \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} [0] & [0] & [0] & [0] & [0] & [-M^{-1}] \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (17)$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} [0] & [0] & [0] & [0] & [1] & [0] \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where A_i in (16) are the radiation sub-matrices corresponding to the sub-indexes, M is the mass and added mass matrix and C_{PTO} is the PTO and friction sub-matrix. In this global state-space system vectors B and C are transformed into matrices. The differential equation system from (15) is solved using a Runge Kutta Method (ode45) implemented in MATLAB. One of the great advantages of this time domain model is its speed: a one hour sea state is solved in approximately 25 s.

3. Validation

The two body heave converter presented by Babarit et al. (2012), see figure 2, has been chosen in order to verify the time domain model described above. A first verification is carried out comparing the time-model results with those obtained using the frequency domain WADAM numerical model and assuming no PTO connection between the two bodies, $C_{PTO} = 0$. In this analysis, the Response Amplitude Operators (RAOs) of both bodies are obtained. The time domain model analysis was run during 1000 s for regular waves of 1 m amplitude and periods corresponding to the frequencies studied

with WADAM. As the time domain model requires some time to stabilize the initial transitory motion, only the amplitude of the last oscillations were taken into account in order to compare with WADAM RAOs results.

Figure 2: Two body heave Converter analyzed

Figure 3 shows the RAOs calculated by WADAM and by time domain models as previously explained. The correspondence between the two lines is almost perfect except for the low period branch near the natural period. This difference is due to the order of the polynomial obtained by the toolbox in Perez and Fossen (2009) because the accuracy of the approximation is very sensitive to the order of the polynomial selected. The selected polynomial has the best approximation in the full range of periods.

Figure 3: RAO of the two body system calculated using frequency domain (WADAM) and time domain

4. Model applications

4.1. Performance analysis

In this section, the time domain model is applied to simulate the performance of the two-body WEC presented in Figure 2. The model is used to analyze the WEC's motion and power absorption under regular and irregular waves. The excitation and radiation forces for irregular waves are calculated assuming that the force of a given irregular sea state can be obtained adding the forces of each wave component of the given sea state.

The instantaneous power is obtained using expression (19) assuming power production to be proportional to the relative velocity between the two bodies:

$$P_i = C_{PTO}(\dot{z}_1 - \dot{z}_2)^2 \quad (19)$$

Figures 4 and 5 represent the behavior of the heave converter analyzed for regular waves of $H = 1m$ and $T = 12s$, and irregular waves of $H_s = 1m$ and $T_p = 12s$. The irregular sea state peak period simulated in Figure 5 is near the natural period of the two body system, explaining why some oscillations are very large.

Figure 4: Motion of the two body system for regular waves of $H = 1m$ and $T = 12s$

4.2. Power Production

The final goal of this paper is to obtain the power production time series and power statistics of the modeled WEC when installed at a given location. For this paper it is assumed that the WEC is installed on the Cantabrian Sea, near the village of Santoña, north Spain. This location was selected

Figure 5: Motion of the two body system for irregular waves of $H_s = 1m$ and $T_p = 12s$

because the local Government is developing a testing area for WECs there. The point selected is $3.46^\circ W$ and $43.56^\circ N$ with a depth of 100 m and yearly averaged power of $24 kW/m$. Figure 8 show the $H_s - T_p$ frequency matrix of the marine climate at this point. In order to compute the power matrix, the C_{PTO} used is the optimum one for each sea state explained in the next subsection.

Figure 6 shows the power matrix of the analyzed WEC. To compute this matrix the model was run for all the 3-hour sea states presented in Figure 6. In the computation of Figure 6 it was assumed that the WEC will enter in survival mode for $H_s > 6$ m. As Figure 6 showS, the power production increases as the wave height increases and the peak period approaches the

natural period. The annual production of the device is obtained multiplying this power matrix by the frequency matrix (see Figure 8) giving an annual energy production of 1414 MWh/year.

Figure 6: Power matrix of the device (kWh)

The net capacity factor (NCF) of a power plant is the ratio of the actual output of a power plant over a period of time and its potential output if operating at full nominal power the entire time. The WEC's NCF depends on the PTO nominal power and should increase as the PTO nominal power decreases. Taking into account that electrical machines can support overcharges over short periods of time, to compute the NCF the Babarit et al. (2012) assumption was used: If the power is between one or two times the nominal power then the generated power will be the nominal one, but if the power exceeds two times the nominal power then the generated power will

Figure 7: Capacity factor vs Nominal Power

be zero.

Figure 7 shows the NCF for the analyzed WEC. The slope represents the net increase of the NCF in terms of the nominal installed power. The optimum installed capacity should be that which presents the maximum slope. As can be seen in Figure 7, this maximum slope is around an installed capacity of 1 MW. This installed power has been used in the following analysis of the WEC.

4.3. Performance optimization and long term analysis

The objective of this section is to carry out the optimization of the PTO constant for the selected wave climate in order to maximize the energy production.

Heave converters usually comprise one the following PTOs:

- Direct linear generators

Figure 8: Percentage occurrence matrix in Santoña (Spain)

- Hydraulic piston-accumulator-hydraulic motor-generator
- Rack and pinion - gearbox - generator

Whatever the PTO selected it is possible to regulate the damping constant (usually through the generator excitation) in order to maximize the wave energy absorption from each sea state. This PTO control can be carried out in two ways 1) setting a fixed optimum value of C_{PTO} for each sea state or 2) instantaneously modifying the C_{PTO} in terms of the incoming waves and the heave motion. This second option will improve the energy production but it implies the instantaneous measurement of the incoming waves and WEC heave motion and a fast response of the control system. In the approach proposed here, option 1 has been chosen, and a new methodology is proposed to select the C_{PTO} that maximizes the energy production for any sea state.

Figure 9: PTO Optimization for different sea states

To fulfill that objective, the numerical model described in section 2 was run for a selected range of irregular sea states with wave heights and peak periods comprising the $H_s - T_p$ occurrence matrix (see Figure 8). For each sea state, a hundred of PTO constants from $1 \cdot 10^5$ to $1 \cdot 10^7$ Kg/s were tested. Figure 9 shows one example of the energy production in terms of the PTO constants for several sea states. As can be seen in this figure, for each sea state there is a optimum value of the C_{PTO} in terms of energy production. Once this optimal C_{PTO} is obtained, the optimal power matrix can be built (see figure 6).

The yearly averaged optimal energy production of the heave device in a given wave climate is usually obtained by multiplying the optimized power

matrix by the $Hs-Tp$ occurrence matrix. If a sea state time series is available at a given location, the sea state time series of optimal energy production can be obtained interpolating each time series sea states on the optimal power matrix.

The previous approach has two main sources of inefficiency: 1) many of the sea states computed to build the optimal power matrix are useless because their probability is zero and 2) if a linear interpolation is used to compute the time series of sea states of optimal power, the changes in the slope on the production matrix are not taken into account. To avoid these inefficiencies, a new methodology to calculate the sea states time series of optimal energy production is proposed below. This methodology is applied to a node of the 60-year reanalysis data base, Global Ocean Waves (GOW) from Reguero et al. (2012) located near Santoña (North Spain) made up of hourly sea states.

The first source of inefficiency is addressed using a selection technique to separate a subset of sea states from the data base that best represent all the data base sea states. In this methodology, the MaxDiss algorithm from Snarey et al. (1997) is proposed because it represents very well the boundaries of the data base in a multidimensional domain. For the second inefficiency source, the Radial Basis Function (RBF) interpolation method from Franke (1982) is used. This methodology has been used previously in Camus et al. (2011) to study the downscaling of wave climate to coastal areas.

The first sea state of the MaxDiss selection procedure is given by the user. Usually, one sea state on the multidimensional data base boundary is chosen (i.e. the sea state of the time series with the maximum H_s). In this case the time series is 2-dimensional (H_s-T_p) and as the objective is the power production, four criteria for the starting sea state are tested, corresponding to the sea state with maximum:

- H_s significant wave height
- H_s^2 square significant wave height
- $H_s^2 T_p$ Energy Flux
- T_p (optimal) Peak period

In order to check the best initial sea state criteria and the optimal size of the selected subset of sea states, a year-long time series of sea states (year 2001, 8737 sea states) of energy production has been computed with the numerical model and with the proposed methodology, using different sizes (50 to 3500) of the MaxDiss subset of sea states and the four criteria indicated above for the initial sea state and the RBF interpolation technique to rebuild the full time series of energy production.

Figure 10 represents the linear correlation coefficient ρ , between the two data sets obtained by, computing the 8737 sea states and, using the proposed methodology (MaxDiss-RBF) computing only a subset of sea states of different sizes and with different starting criteria. As can be seen in the figure, the best criterion for the Max-Diss starting sea state is that which uses the

maximum Hs^2Tp sea state. Also note that with subset sizes larger than 200 sea states, all four criteria for the starting sea state provide similar accuracy.

Figure 10: r-squared parameter for the different selection cases and the different number of cases

The complexity of the MaxDiss+RBF methodology is justified here in terms of precision with respect to the traditional method of multiplying the frequency and power matrices. To compare the accuracy of the proposed methodology with the traditional one, the 2001 year series was reconstructed by interpolating each time series sea states on the $14 \times 14 = 196$ sea states of the power matrix using the RBF technique, using the proposed methodology with a MaxDiss subset of sea states with the same size as the power matrix (196 cases) and rebuilding the full year time series using the RBF technique.

The correlation coefficients between the true time series of sea states

Model	274
Power Matrix*Ocurrence matrix	147
Equally spaced Power Matrix+RBF	190
MaxDiss+RBF	245

Table 1: Mean hourly annual power in Kwh calculated with the metrologies selected for year 2001

power production and the reconstructed ones was 0.96 for the proposed methodology and 0.7 for the one using the power matrix and the RBF interpolation technique. In Table 1, the yearly averaged energy production is computed using: 1) the time series of sea states energy production obtained by computing all 8737 sea states, 2) the product of power and frequency matrices, (196 sea states computed) 3) the time series of sea states energy production reconstructed using the power matrix and RBF (196 cases computed) and 4) the proposed MaxDiss+RBF methodology computing 196 cases. As can be noted, the percentage difference between each method and the exact are 46% for method 2, 31% for method 3 and 11% for the proposed methodology. Figure 11 shows the contribution of each sea state of the frequency matrix to the relative error on the yearly averaged energy production computed using method 2. The maximum error is located around the 10 s peak period, where the power matrix has a local ridge and the frequency matrix nears it maximum and the concavity of the power production matrix provides the interpolation of each sea state energy production always below the true one. Finally, figure 13 shows the MaxDiss selected subset of sea

Figure 11: Percentage of relative error with respect mean annual hourly production between methodologies Occurrence Matrix* Power Matrix and power matrix calculated by the model for year 2001

states concentrated on the $Hs-Tp$ region where sea states are probable (192 points on the 90% probability volume) while using the equally-spaced power matrix, only 121 points are in the same volume.

Taking into account that the proposed methodology only computes 2% of the sea states of the data set, it is clear the advantage of the new methodology. Also the inaccuracy of the traditional methodologies used to compute de yearly-mean of energy power production o to rebuild the full time series have been demonstrated.

If the range of the sea state variables does not change,neither does the

number of sea states on the MaxDiss subset. For example, the full 60-year hourly sea states time series of energy production can be rebuilt with similar accuracy computing the energy production of only 200 sea states with the numerical model. Figure 13 represents the yearly mean and the standard deviation of the 60 year rebuilt time series using 200 and 1000 subset of sea states in the MaxDiss selection. Moreover there is no noticeable difference between the two curves. The average power produced by the device is $300kW$, being the worst year in terms of production 1962 with $260kW$ and the best year 1960 with $340kW$. Therefore, with the methodology presented in this paper the most important statistics of the life cycle of a wave converter can be obtained in a reliable way.

Figure 12: Selected cases for the two methodologies applied for the year 2001

Figure 13: Mean annual power and standard deviation for the 60 year series at the study with 200 and 1000 cases

5. Conclusions

In this paper, the frequency-domain identification of Perez and Fossen and the state-space transformation of Yu and Falnes have been used to develop a time-domain numerical model. This model has been used to check the behavior of a two-body heaving WEC. After validation of the time-domain model using the WADAM frequency-domain numerical code, the WEC performance in a given wave climate has been optimized assuming that the PTO's damping is optimal in terms of energy absorption and constant during each sea state.

The developed numerical model has shown to be accurate and efficient in terms of computer time and provides a good tool to analyze the response of

a WEC and also has the advantage to allow the implementation of non linear forces (i.e. drag or PTO forces) or complex control methodologies based on the actual position or velocity of the WEC. Running the model for different damping constants and sea states has shown that there is always a PTO damping constant that maximizes the WEC's energy capture. Using that optimal damping, and with some control strategies imposed for the WEC survival in high seas, the optimal energy production sea-state time series for a 60 year period has been calculated at a selected point in Northern Spain. A new methodology, based on the MaxDiss selection technique and on the RBF multilinear interpolation, has been implemented to select the subset of sea-states to be computed with the numerical model and used to rebuild the 60-year time series of sea-state energy production. This new methodology has been shown to be more accurate (for the same computational effort) than the traditional one that uses the power and occurrence matrices.

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